

LEGAL NATURE OF INTERNATIONAL COMMERCIAL ARBITRATION

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Abstract: International commercial arbitration is a crucial mechanism for resolving cross-border business disputes, offering a private and binding alternative to litigation. This article explores the legal nature of international commercial arbitration, examining its foundations in both contract and international law. Key elements such as the arbitration agreement, the role of arbitral institutions, and the enforceability of arbitral awards under the New York Convention are analyzed. The article also addresses the interplay between national courts and arbitral tribunals, highlighting the principles of party autonomy and procedural flexibility. Through a comparative analysis of various legal systems, the article sheds light on the evolving jurisprudence and the challenges faced in maintaining the balance between sovereignty and the global harmonization of arbitration practices.

Key words: alternative dispute resolution, international commercial arbitration, New York Convention, awards, arbitration agreement, party autonomy, choice of law.

Relevance of the study. The dynamics of dispute resolution, privacy, flexibility, efficiency - these are the main distinguishing features that make arbitration attractive to the business entities.

The institution of international commercial arbitration has only recently begun to develop in Uzbekistan. In particular, since 1996 Uzbekistan has been a party to the 1958 New York Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards. Uzbekistan’s accession to this Convention plays a key role, as it is this Convention that lays the foundation for the recognition and enforcement of international arbitration agreements and awards.

Of particular importance for the development of international commercial arbitration was the establishment of the Tashkent International Arbitration Center (TIAC) at the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the status of a non-governmental non-profit organization by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4001 dated November 5, 2018.¹⁵

The object of the study is the nature of international commercial arbitration.

Purpose of the study. Comprehensive, scientific and theoretical analysis of international commercial arbitration and the conflict of legal cultures within its framework. And also to conduct a comprehensive analysis of significant theoretical and practical problems related to the conflict of cultures in international commercial arbitration.

Objectives of the study. The conducted study determined develop the comprehensive analysis of the concept and essence of international commercial arbitration.

Analysis of scientific articles. Studies of the conflict of legal cultures in international commercial arbitration have been conducted mainly by foreign specialists and have been much more widely developed in the works of Stefen Kroll, Gary Born, Jean Paulson, Maxi Schroer and so on.¹⁶

Methodology. The methodological basis of the study was a wide range of methods of scientific research - comparative-legal, system-legal, structural, logical analysis and others. Study and analysis of literature to identify existing studies and theories.

Arbitration as a dispute resolution mechanism is becoming popular in light of the recent expansion of economic, trade and investment relations between legal entities and states. It is noteworthy that the more popular arbitration becomes, the more domestic problems arise. Arbitration is the preferred dispute resolution

¹⁵ Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Establishment of the Tashkent International Arbitration Center (TIAC) under the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan .

¹⁶ Cambridge Compendium of International Commercial and Investment Arbitration, Stefan Kroll, Cambridge University Press, 2023; Gary B. Born, International Arbitration: Law and Practice, Kluwer Law International, 2012; Jan Paulsson, "The Idea of Arbitration", Oxford University Press, 2013; International Arbitration and the Covid-19 Revolution, by Maxi Scherer (Author), Niuscha Bassiri (Author), Mohamed S. Abdel Wahab (Author), & 6 more, Wolters Kluwer, 2020.

mechanism in international business. Although arbitration remains popular mainly among large corporations and certain business circles, arbitration continues to play an important role in international commerce.

Speaking about the legal nature of international commercial arbitration, it is impossible not to emphasize the opinion of Gary Bourne, who believes that arbitration is a process in which the parties by mutual agreement submit a dispute to a non-governmental body chosen by or for the benefit of the parties to render a binding decision resolving the dispute in accordance with neutral, adjudicative procedures that give each party the opportunity to present its case.¹⁷ Grounds for choosing arbitration as the dispute resolution mechanism:

Impartiality. One of the main purposes of international arbitration agreements is to provide a neutral forum for dispute resolution, separate from the parties and their respective government of government states. Parties often begin negotiations on dispute resolution mechanisms to ensure that disputes are resolved in the court they find most favorable to them - often local courts. These will be convenient and familiar to the hometown party; they are also likely to be inconvenient and unfamiliar to the counterparty. However, the characteristics that make one party's local courts attractive to the other. However, the characteristics that make one party's local courts attractive to one party often make them unacceptable to the counterparties. As a consequence, outside of credit and similar transactions, it is often impossible for either party to get either party to agree to resolve disputes in their local courts. In such circumstances, agreement should almost always be sought on a suitable neutral forum - a dispute resolution forum that does not benefit either party, but gives each party the opportunity to present its case to an objective and impartial tribunal. The result, in most cases, is an agreement to arbitrate (or, less frequently, to litigate) in a neutral court. For example, a French and a Mexican company may agree to arbitrate their disputes in Miami, Spain or England, while an American and a Japanese or German company may agree to have their disputes heard in Switzerland, England, Canada. dispute resolution in Switzerland, England, Canada or Singapore. Simply

¹⁷ Gary B. Born, *International Arbitration: Law and Practice*, Kluwer Law International, 2012, p 34.

put, a party will usually agree to arbitration not because arbitration is the most favorable possible forum, but because it is the least unfavorable forum that a party can get in arm's length negotiations.

Effective enforcement of agreements and awards. One of the purposes of modern legal regimes for international arbitration is to facilitate the enforcement of arbitration agreements and awards. In particular, as international arbitration conventions (notably the New York Convention),¹⁸ and arbitration law (in particular the UNCITRAL Model Law) ensure that international arbitration agreements are more easily and quickly enforceable and more broadly interpreted than forum selection clauses. This is consistently cited as a major advantage of international arbitration. In contrast, there are only a few regional agreements aimed at creating effective international enforcement regimes for forum selection clauses. The most notable of these is the Brussels I Regulation in the European Union,¹⁹ which provides for the enforceability of forum selection agreements defining the courts of EU Member States, subject only to limited exceptions. There are also several sectoral agreements that provide enforcement mechanisms for international forum selection agreements (e.g., treaties governing maritime transportation of goods).

In contrast, there are only a few regional agreements on the enforceability of foreign court judgments (particularly with respect to foreign courts) and no global equivalent to the New York Convention for foreign judgments. Some major trading states, including the U.S., are not party to bilateral or multilateral agreements on the enforceability of foreign judgments. In the absence of international treaties, the recognition of foreign judgments depends on local law, which often makes it difficult, if not impossible, to enforce them effectively. As a consequence, it is usually much more likely that an award will be recognized under local law.

The likelihood that an arbitral award will be enforced abroad (thereby ending the parties' dispute) is generally much higher than a foreign judgment. In addition to the comparatively greater enforceability of arbitration agreements, the more reliable

¹⁸ Конвенция Организации Объединенных Наций о признании и приведении в исполнение иностранных арбитражных решений (Нью-Йорк, 10 июня 1958 года).

¹⁹ Regulation (EU) No 1215/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2012 on jurisdiction and the recognition and enforcement of judgments in civil and commercial matters.

enforceability of arbitral awards is one of the main goals and attractions of international arbitration.

Competence and expertise. Another important goal of international arbitration is to provide a competent, expert dispute resolution process. Arbitration has historically been preferred by users because it offers a more expert and experienced means of resolving commercial disputes. This remains the case today, with empirical studies emphasizing the importance of arbitrators' commercial experience in deciding whether to use international arbitration.

Finality of awards. Another distinctive feature of international arbitration is the absence, in most cases, of extensive appellate review of arbitral awards. Judicial review of awards in most developed countries is limited to issues of jurisdiction, procedural fairness, and public policy, and relies heavily on the arbitrators' decisions on the merits (as discussed below). This contrasts markedly with the accessibility of appellate review of first-instance decisions, where national law allows for a fairly thorough review of legal, and often factual, issues. There are both advantages and disadvantages to the general inaccessibility of appellate review of decisions.

The waiver of appellate review significantly reduces court costs and delays (especially when a successful appeal means that the case must be retried in the first instance court). On the other hand, it also means that an erroneous award cannot be easily corrected. Overall, anecdotal and empirical evidence suggests that business users prefer the efficiency and finality of arbitration procedures, even at the expense of appellate rights. There are also some jurisdictions in which parties have the option, with or without a judicial review contract, to obtain some measure of appellate review of arbitrators' decisions on the merits.

Party autonomy and procedural flexibility. Another purpose and intended benefit of international arbitration is to promote party autonomy and procedural flexibility. As discussed below, international arbitration conventions and national laws provide parties with broad autonomy to agree on the substantive law and procedures applicable to arbitration proceedings. In practice, one of the main reasons for granting procedural autonomy to parties is to enable them to dispense with the

technical formalities of national proceedings and instead tailor the procedures to their particular disputes. Some categories of disputes require specialized procedures for expert evidence, expedited procedures where time is critical, or mechanisms designed for particular commercial markets. In general, parties are generally free to agree on the timetable for the arbitration process, the availability and scope of disclosure, the manner in which facts and expert evidence will be presented, the length of hearings, and other matters. The ability of parties to adopt flexible procedures is one of the main attractions of international arbitration - again supported by empirical evidence.

Arbitration establishes a distinctive framework of applicable law governing various aspects of arbitration. Unlike litigation, arbitration is always a matter of agreement between the parties and even involves deviation from established laws and rules if the parties so agree. Arbitration goes beyond existing legal rules, state-controlled legal vacuums and establishes its own set of laws that apply to a particular case. Therefore, the question of applicable law is really complex because the parties come from different legal systems, they can choose a different set of rules separately for the procedural and substantive parts of the contract, and consider the application of a soft law tool.

It is often said that parties to a contract make their own law, and it is certainly true that, subject to public policy rules and parties are free to negotiate such terms as they may choose. Nevertheless, agreements intended to be legally enforceable (as opposed to purely socially enforceable) create legal rights and obligations, and legal rights and obligations cannot exist in a vacuum but must have a place in a legal system that can address issues such as the validity, application and interpretation of contracts, and generally supplement their express provisions.

In general, most multinational companies prefer and actively seek the confidentiality and secrecy that the arbitration process provides. Confidentiality reduces the risk of escalating the parties' dispute, limits collateral damage from the dispute, and focuses the parties on amicable, businesslike resolution of differences.

However, it is important to recognize that international commercial arbitration also has some disadvantages that must be considered. Below, we examine some of

these disadvantages and discuss their implications for parties involved in international commercial arbitration.

High Cost: International commercial arbitration can be expensive, especially if the parties cannot reach agreement on the rules and procedures that will govern the arbitration. In addition, parties may be required to pay the fees and expenses of the arbitrator(s), as well as legal representation and other costs associated with the arbitration.

Limited Appeal Rights: In most cases, parties have a limited ability to appeal an arbitration award. This means that parties may be left with a decision that they believe is unfair or incorrect.

In conclusion, international commercial arbitration has a number of advantages and disadvantages that should be carefully considered by the parties before deciding to utilize this form of dispute resolution. While arbitration offers flexibility, confidentiality, expertise and enforceability, it can also be expensive, limit the right to appeal, restrict disclosure and lack precedential value. Ultimately, parties must weigh these factors and make a decision based on their particular needs and circumstances.

One of the major disadvantages of international commercial arbitration is its cost, which can be prohibitive for some parties, especially small companies or individuals. Another disadvantage is the lack of a formal appeals process, which means that an arbitral tribunal's decision is final and binding, even if it contains errors of law or fact.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

I. International Acts:

1. UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Arbitration (1985), as amended in 2006;
2. United Nations Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (New York, June 10, 1958);

3. United Nations Convention on Contracts for the International Sale of Goods (Vienna, 1980) (CISG).

II. Regulatory and Legal Acts:

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III. Scientific literature, textbooks, monographs, articles:

1. Stefan Kroll, Cambridge Compendium of International Commercial and Investment Arbitration, Cambridge University Press, 2023;

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